

1 **Control of Viperin by HPV16 E5.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We used next generation sequencing to describe in an unbiased fashion molecular functions of the E5
7 protein of high-risk HPV16 versus that of HPV84, a lower risk type. We demonstrate here specific control
8 of Viperin encoded by *Rsad2* by type 16 HPV E5. *Iqgap2* was instead a shared HPV16 and HPV84 E5
9 cellular target.

10 Citations

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